

Event-based control for IPTD processes with simple tuning methods

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Abstract— The event-based control of IPTD (*Integrator Plus Time Delay*) processes is investigated in this study. A two-degree-of-freedom (2-DOF) structure with simple tuning methods is proposed to cope with the set-point tracking and the load disturbance rejection tasks. A stability analysis is conducted and a simple tuning methodology is provided. Simulation results prove the effectiveness of the approach.

I. INTRODUCTION

Event-based approaches appear to be a promising alternative in process control whose aim is to achieve a satisfactory trade-off between the sources usage and the closed-loop performance [1]. These techniques can be significantly beneficial for some constrained applications (typically in energy and bandwidth) as a way to reduce the control-loop degradation produced by network congestion [2]. The emerging networked control systems (NCS) are a valuable example of this trade-off [3].

Despite the fact that last decade has been prolific in analytical results and many techniques have been proposed for the design of event-based Proportional-Integral-Derivative (PID) controllers [4], the design of an efficient control scheme, as well as systematic tuning method, is still a challenging problem. Note that the event condition may be any mathematical function (see [5] for typical event-based conditions), thus obtaining different architectures and nonlinear responses [6]. Particularly, when wireless communications are considered, the protocol constraints and energy consumption need to be considered as a part of the control loop design [7]. Consequently, this kind of systems usually considers more tuning parameters in comparison with traditional time-based control systems.

Nevertheless, some noticeable advances have been made. There is a general consensus on the sampling algorithm, being Send-On-Delta (SOD) the commonest (see [8]–[10]). Such an algorithm consists in computing a new sample when a signal changes more than a predefined threshold Δ instead of using a sampling period. On the other hand, the use of hybrid sampling schemes, that is, those that combine time-based and event-based sampling schemes in agents involved in the closed-loop, have become one of the most extended design approaches. In this way, the designer can rely on the well-known automatic control theory to explain the event-based behavior [11]. Some representative approaches based on time-event-based hybrid implementations can be consulted in [4], [5], [11]. Regarding the tuning of event-

based controllers, it is worth mentioning the works of [1], [12]–[20], where ad hoc approaches are proposed.

Unfortunately, most event-based approaches address the control of self-regulating processes because of the difficulties involved in analysis of unstable and integrating processes. From an industrial perspective, this is a drawback because a wide range of processes presents integration in its dynamics, which can sometimes be well represented as IPTD processes [21]. For this reason, the event-based control of IPTD processes is investigated in this work.

In this context, a two degree-of-freedom control system based on events is proposed. The control scheme and the tuning methodology are based on the results of [19]. Following this approach to design the scheme, the problems of avoiding the limit cycles and choosing the tuning parameters can be clearly separated, such that the tuning task can be carried out with a simple and effective methodology to meet the design specifications [19]. Thus, the approach is extended to consider IPTD processes, deriving a sufficient stability condition, as well as a simple tuning method.

This paper is organized as follows: in Section II, the architecture of the event-based control system is introduced. In Section III, the behavior of the system is described. A stability analysis is developed in Section IV. The tuning methodology is provided in Section V. The results from simulation are presented in Sections VI, and, finally, Section VII presents the main conclusions.

Figure 1. General scheme of the event-based control system. Solid lines denote time-based signals, and dashed lines event-based signal transmission.

Figure 2. Blocks and signals involved in the event-based system. The element α acts as an interruptor using the discrete values 0 and 1.

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II. EVENT-BASED CONTROL ARCHITECTURE

The general structure of the event-based control system is shown in Figure 1. The scheme is composed of three blocks: The controller, the process plant, and the event generator. This structure represents a small variation with respect to the generic scheme introduced in [22] where the observer is integrated with the event generator. According to this approach, event-based sampling is used for the error signal and regular time-based sampling is used for the remaining signals. In this context, each time an event occurs, a new error sample is sent to the controller and its value is hold until new events are triggered.

The stability properties and the tuning methodology developed in this work are designed by considering an IPTD process in Figure 1 as described by

$$P(s) = \frac{K}{s} e^{-Ls} \quad (1)$$

where K is the process gain (which is assumed to be positive without loss of generality) and $L \geq 0$ is the process delay. The process is assumed to be affected by non-modeled step disturbances $d(t)$ at the input $u(t)$ and a set-point value $r(t)$ is demanded.

The next block described is the controller $C(s)$. Here, it is used the simplest standard controller, which is given by a P (proportional) controller defined by the gain (2).

$$C(s) = K_p \quad (2)$$

The gain K_p represents the first degree-of-freedom of the event-based system which is used to define the speed of the set-point response.

From the general structure in Figure 1, a more detailed representation is described in Figure 2. For clarity, the block of the event generator is now described. This block characterizes the control loop as an event-based control system and it is divided into two complementary parts: a prediction unit (based on the Smith predictor structure) and a sampling unit (based on the SSOD sampling algorithm). The aim of the sampling unit is to measure and to send an error sample to the controller each time the event condition is satisfied. This task is performed using the SSOD event-based sampling algorithm, which considers two parameters: a predefined event threshold Δ and an internal state j , where $\Delta \in \mathbb{R}^+$ and $j \in \mathbb{Z}$ (see [23]).

Figure 3. Quantization relationship between $e(t)$ and $e^*(t)$.

According to this algorithm, if $e(t)$ represents the instantaneous error, and $e^*(t)$ the sampled error sent to the controller, the relationship between them is defined as an integer multiple j of the threshold Δ in the form $e^*(t) = j\Delta$. Thus, the event-based signal $e^*(t)$ changes to the upper or lower quantization value when the time-based signal $e(t)$ increases or decreases more than the quantity of Δ with respect to the last sample as described in Figure 3 and the equation (5). The prediction unit is defined using the scheme of the Smith predictor with the aim of compensating the process delay in the set-point tracking task in favor of events are triggered at the required instants. Therefore, it includes, respectively, a model of the controller, $\bar{C}(s)$, a model of the process with delay, $\bar{P}(s)$, and another without delay, $\bar{P}_0(s)$ as follows:

$$\bar{P}_0(s) = \frac{\bar{K}}{\bar{\tau}s + 1} \quad \bar{P}(s) = \bar{P}_0(s)e^{-\bar{L}s} \quad \bar{C}(s) = C(s) \quad (3)$$

The notations \bar{K} , $\bar{\tau}$ and \bar{L} are used to consider the identified parameters used in the Smith predictor model. The signal $\nabla y(t)$ describes the output deviations between the process plant $P(s)$ and the model $\bar{P}(s)$. The emulated feedback signal called $y_r(t)$ (in advance, the feedback signal) represents the feedback signal that would have the equivalent time-based system (i.e., if the sampling unit was omitted). This signal is considered basic for understanding the events-based behavior of the proposed system and, according to Figure 3 is calculated as $y(t) + \bar{y}_0(t) - \bar{y}(t)$.

The second degree-of-freedom is used to regulate the disturbance rejection response. Due to the nature of the process, the rejection of step disturbances entails a difficult task without a time-based observation and actuation. For this reason, bidirectional communication with the plant is required in the presence of disturbances to effectively compensate its influence. According to the proposed structure, the disturbance is estimated in the event generator side using the information contained in the process output signal $y(t)$. When disturbances occur, the difference between the model and process outputs in steady state is an estimation of the amplitude of $d(t)$. Thus, using the block K_d this estimated value is introduced in the loop to eliminate the effect of the disturbance. As will be explained later, the compensation signal is only introduced when a disturbance is detected as a medium to reduce the sampling effort between block dependencies.

III. CONTROL SYSTEM RESPONSE

First, for the sake of clarity, some concepts and notations are a priori defined:

- j : This subscript indicates the current state of the SSOD algorithm.
- t_j : Time instant in which the state j was reached (and the sample e^*_j sent to the controller).
- e^*_j : Represents the last sample sent to the controller (at the instant t_j). Its value corresponds to $e^*_j = j\Delta$.
- T_j : Time interval between events or states. It is also defined as $T_j = T_{j \rightarrow j-1} = [t_j, t_{j-1})$, where j represents the last state reached, and $j-1$ the next (assuming that the error is decreasing).

$$\left| \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} e_0(t) \right| < \Delta \quad (11)$$

Thus, to demonstrate the practical stability of the event-based system, it has to be demonstrated both the existence of the equilibrium point as well as its reach.

Firstly, a requirement to ensure that the equilibrium point can be found is that the stability of the time-based inner loop defined by the compensator K_d has to be guaranteed. As K_d acts as a feedback controller, it must be tuned to achieve closed-loop stability and also an adequate transient of the disturbance rejection response. According to (6), its stability depends on the roots of the characteristic equation $s + K_d K e^{-Ls} = 0$. An adequate tuning rule to achieve stable transient response can be derived by imposing a minimum phase margin of 60° so that the gain K_d can be tuned as:

$$K_d < \frac{1}{2KL} \quad (12)$$

Once the condition for tuning the gain K_d is obtained, the condition for the existence of the equilibrium point can be derived. For brevity, the simplified notations are used and large demonstrations are omitted. The inequality (11) is equivalent to (13).

$$|r| - \Delta < \left| \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} y_{r_0}(t_0 + t) \right| < |r| + \Delta \quad (13)$$

This means that, if the final value reached by the signal $y_r(t)$ after the zero error event-based sample is triggered remains enclosed in a range $(-\Delta, \Delta)$ around the set-point value, new events will not occur and therefore, the system will have reached an equilibrium point. If the expression for $y_r(t)$ in the inequality (13) is developed as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} y_{r_0}(t_0 + t) \right| \\ &= \left| K_p \bar{K} t e^*_{r_0}(t_0) + \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \gamma_0(t_0 + t) + y_{r_0}(t_0) \right| = \\ &= |\gamma_0(t_0 + \max\{L, \bar{L}\})| \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

the final condition for evaluating the existence of the equilibrium point is obtained as

$$|\gamma_0(t_0 + \max\{L, \bar{L}\})| < \Delta \quad (15)$$

that denotes the progress of the extra dynamics after the event-based sample of the zero error value is reached. Thus, the initial condition $y_{r_0}(t_0)$ is displaced by quantity of $\gamma_0(t_0 + \max\{L, \bar{L}\})$, which in turn depends on the displacements γ_j produced in previous states j . Obviously, an additional displacement of $\pm\Delta$ in the deadband would be undesirable because new events would be triggered and limit cycles may even appear. For this reason, the bound of (15) defines the existence of the equilibrium point.

Since the computation of $\gamma_0(t_0 + \max\{L, \bar{L}\})$ requires the use of numerical and recursive methods, a more conservative condition to guarantee the stability can be used. It can be easily demonstrated that $\gamma_{j_{max-1}}(\cdot) > \gamma_{j_{max-2}}(\cdot) > \dots > \gamma_2(\cdot) > \gamma_1(\cdot) > \gamma_0(\cdot)$. Therefore, rather than computing $\gamma_0(\cdot)$, it is more useful to evaluate whether any of values $\gamma_j(\cdot)$ satisfies the condition (15). In this context, a simple condition that can be evaluated without the need of recursive algorithms is given by (16).

$$\begin{aligned} & |\gamma_{j_{max-1}}| = \\ &= \left| \frac{K_p}{K_d K} e^*_{j_{max}} \left[K \left(1 - e^{-\frac{L}{\tau}} \right) - \bar{K} \left(1 - e^{-\frac{\bar{L}}{\tau}} \right) \right] \right| < \Delta \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

which is the condition proposed in this work. Thus, if the conditions (12) and (16) are satisfied, as well as a time-based actuation can be enabled to compensate the disturbances, it can be stated that the system will have an equilibrium point in the presence of modeling errors and load step disturbances.

Remark 2: The condition (16) defines a sufficient condition (but not necessary) to evaluate the system stability. This solution provides a range of values for the tuning parameters that ensure the stability but this solution is biased and could be more precise if the value γ_0 was explicitly calculated by using recursive methods or by simulations.

The second part of the proposition consists of demonstrating the reach of the equilibrium point. It can be easily demonstrated by differentiating the equation (4) including disturbances and by using the final value theorem

$$\dot{e}_j(t) = -\dot{y}_{r_j}(t) \simeq -K_p \bar{K} e^*_{r_j} \quad (17)$$

thus demonstrating that the system tends to zero state value despite uncertainty and disturbances and that the convergence speed depends strongly on the parameter K_p . Therefore, if the equilibrium point exists, the event-based system will be GUUB for a given set-point r .

V. TUNING METHODOLOGY

A significant result of the approach used to design the event generator is that the response of the event-based system can be predicted with reasonable precision. Using this property, the concept of tuning regions was introduced as a medium to develop the tuning procedure (see [19]). Tuning regions are parameter spaces that relate a performance index to tuning parameters (K_p, Δ) . From the point of view of the system performance, the parameter Δ controls the distance (in magnitude) between two consecutive events and therefore the resulting number of events and the parameter K_p regulates how fast the response converges to the set-point value and furthermore, it is directly related to both the control effort and the capability of reducing the control error. Thus, from tuning parameters (K_p, Δ) , tuning regions are obtained using a set of characteristic performance indexes, which are defined to describe the general features of the closed loop response:

- The T_{ST} (Settling Time).

$$T_{ST} = L + \frac{a}{|j_{max}| \Delta K K_p} + \sum_{j=|j_{max}|}^1 \frac{\Delta}{j \Delta K K_p} \quad (18)$$

where j_{max} and a represent the quotient and the remainder of the integer division $r \div \Delta$, respectively.

- IAE (Integrated Absolute Control Error)

$$\begin{aligned} IAE &= \int_0^{T_{ST}} |e(t)| dt = \\ &= |Lr| + \sum_{j=j_{max}}^1 \int_0^{T_j} \left| r - \left(j \Delta K_p K t + y_{r_j}(t_j) \right) \right| dt \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

- The IAU (Integrated Absolute Control Signal)

$$IAU = \frac{\int_0^{T_{ST}} |u(t)| dt}{T_{ST}} = \frac{\sum_{j=j_{max}}^1 \int_0^{T_j} |j\Delta K_P T_j| dt}{T_{ST}} \quad (20)$$

where values T_j are:

$$T_j = \begin{cases} \frac{\Delta + a}{KK_P \Delta j} & j = j_{max} \\ \vdots & \vdots \\ 1 & j \in [j_{max} - 1, 1] \\ \vdots & \vdots \\ \frac{1}{KK_P j} & j \in [j_{max} - 1, 1] \end{cases} \quad (21)$$

- The S (Sampling Effort):

$$S = 2(r \div \Delta) \quad (22)$$

Figure 5 shows an illustrative example of tuning regions based on the mentioned performance indexes for $K = 1$, $L = 5$, and $r = 1$. The use of tuning regions is very interactive because they show direct information about the performance of the control strategy and the sampling technique. White dashed vertical lines define areas with the same expected number of events and therefore the same sampling effort. In this way, these areas intuitively show the evolution of the settling time, the tracking error as well as the control effort for a specific sampling effort. In this context, given a generic IPTD system and a set-point r , tuning regions can be pre-computed and used to define tuning parameters. Note that any other index could also have been considered.

Remark 3: Tuning regions are calculated considering an accurate IPTD model. In the non-ideal case, tuning regions will not correspond exactly with system responses, but such an assumption will not impose a great restriction on the predicted system performance while (16) is satisfied.

VI. RESULTS

In this section, simulation results are provided. In particular, the system performance and tuning methodology are evaluated using the IPTD process and the high-order process in (23) (from [24]). The second one was approximated as an IPTD model with the half rule (see [25]).

Figure 5. Illustrative examples of tuning regions for the process P_1 in (23)

$$P_1(s) = \frac{1}{s} e^{-5s}$$

$$P_2(s) = \frac{(0.175s + 1)^2}{s(s + 1)(0.02s + 1)} \quad \bar{P}_2(s) \approx \frac{1}{s} e^{-1.69s} \quad (23)$$

In the first experiment, the influence of the first degree of freedom K_p is analyzed for the process P_1 . Here, the robustness of the control strategy is also evaluated by considering a modeling error in the range of -10% in the identification of the set of parameters (K, L). The parameter Δ is set equal to a 10% of the set-point value. Under this scenario, the bound of K_p that satisfies the stability condition (16) gives 0.107. As can be observed in Figure 6, all designs achieve a stable response but the violation of the condition (16) (dash-dot line design) produces an initial overshoot that makes the output response to exceed the equilibrium point given by the deadband. In this case, despite the stability cannot be a priori ensured, the process becomes stable (note that (16) defines a sufficient but not necessary condition). It is important to notice that, because nonlinear behavior of the event-based system, this could have achieved a limit cycle around the equilibrium point or become unstable.

Simulations produce an adequate correspondence with numerical values when stability condition is fulfilled because deviations of the performance indexes are kept close to the expected values. As predicted by the tuning regions, the larger the gain K_p is, the more reduced are the settling time and the IAE index at the expense of larger control efforts. Although all designs consider the same event threshold, they do not produce similar sampling efforts because the violation of the condition (16) produced by the dash-dot response.

The second degree of freedom, which is focused on the disturbance rejection performance, is evaluated in Figure 7 by considering the same process and uncertainty conditions of the previous experiment. In this case, the value of K_p has been defined as 0.1, which satisfies the stability condition (12) for each design, except for the dot line response. The method for enabling the compensator consists in evaluating variations in the gradient of the signal $\nabla y(t)$ in the absence of set-point changes. Different levels of performance can be encountered modifying the parameter K_d . As can be observed, the violation of the condition (12) deteriorates the stability of the system producing oscillatory responses. This result is improved for the other cases (dashed and dash-dot lines responses), where the stability condition is satisfied. Conversely, if the compensator would not be enabled, the disturbance could not be rejected, as occurred in solid line.

The case of control under unstructured uncertainty is simulated in Figure 8 for the process P_2 . Here, the IPTD approximated model \bar{P}_2 is used to design the parameters of the event-based system (K_p, K_d, Δ). The parameter K_d is set as 0.3 for experiments, but in order to evaluate the robustness with this kind of uncertainty, three values of K_p are considered. These values are computed assuming that exist structured uncertainty in the model \bar{P}_2 , following the same aforementioned methodology. Particularly, the dash-dot line response does not fulfill the condition (16). As expected, larger control actions are produced for greater values of K_p . This has influence on the transient response, achieving better settling times, but could reduce the relative stability.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

A new event-based scheme focused on IPTD processes with a simple tuning methodology has been described. Another aspect addressed has been the design of specific performance indexes to evaluate the results of the transient response and the sampling technique. The importance of the degrees of freedom provided as well as the significant of results is demonstrated in simulation by considering both cases of structured and unstructured uncertainty. The future works are focused on the application of this methodology in a real process plant as well as the development of other time-based compensation schemes for load disturbances that reduced the sampling effort demanded.

Figure 6. Evaluation of the first degree-of-freedom in the presence of uncertainty for the process P_1 .

Figure 7. Evaluation of the second degree-of-freedom in the presence of uncertainty and load disturbances for the process P_1 .

Figure 8. Evaluation of the event-based control scheme in the presence of unstructured uncertainty and load disturbances for the process P_2 .

REFERENCES

- [1] J. Sánchez, A. Visioli, and S. Dormido, "A two-degree-of-freedom PI controller based on events," *J. Process Control*, vol. 21, no. 4, pp. 639–651, Apr. 2011.
- [2] A. Willig, "Recent and Emerging Topics in Wireless Industrial Communications: A Selection," *IEEE Trans. Ind. Informatics*, vol. 4, no. 2, pp. 102–124, May 2008.
- [3] R. A. Gupta and M. Y. Chow, "Networked Control System: Overview and Research Trends," *IEEE Trans. Ind. Electron.*, vol. 57, no. 7, pp. 2527–2535, Jul. 2010.
- [4] J. Sánchez, A. Visioli, and S. Dormido, "Event-based PID control," in *PID Control in the Third Millennium*, Springer, 2012, pp. 495–526.
- [5] J. Sánchez, M. Á. Guarnes, and S. Dormido, "On the Application of Different Event-Based Sampling Strategies to the Control of a Simple Industrial Process," *Sensors*, vol. 9, no. 9, pp. 6795–6818, 2009.
- [6] V. Vasyutynskyy and K. Kabitzsch, "Event-based control: Overview and generic model," in *Proceedings of the IEEE International Workshop on Factory Communication Systems*, 2010, pp. 271–279.
- [7] G. Anastasi, M. Conti, M. Di Francesco, and A. Passarella, "Energy conservation in wireless sensor networks: A survey," *Ad Hoc Networks*, vol. 7, no. 3, pp. 537–568, May 2009.
- [8] M. Miskowicz, "Send-On-Delta Concept: An Event-Based Data Reporting Strategy," *Sensors*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 49–63, Jan. 2006.
- [9] E. Kofman and J. H. Braslavsky, "Level Crossing Sampling in Feedback Stabilization under Data-Rate Constraints," in *Proceedings of the 45th IEEE Conference on Decision and Control*, 2006, pp. 4423–4428.
- [10] V. Vasyutynskyy and K. Kabitzsch, "Towards Comparison of Deadband Sampling Types," in *Proceedings of the IEEE International Symposium on Industrial Electronics*, 2007, vol. 00, pp. 2899–2904.
- [11] S. Dormido, J. Sánchez, and E. Kofman, "Muestreo, control y comunicación basados en eventos," *Rev. Iberoam. Automática e Informática Ind.*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 5–26, 2008.
- [12] M. Beschi, S. Dormido, J. Sánchez, and A. Visioli, "Characterization of symmetric send-on-delta PI controllers," *J. Process Control*, vol. 22, no. 10, pp. 1930–1945, 2012.
- [13] M. Beschi, S. Dormido, J. Sánchez, and A. Visioli, "Tuning of symmetric send-on-delta PI controllers," *IET Control Theory Appl.*, vol. 8, no. 4, pp. 248–259, 2014.
- [14] A. Leva and A. V. Papadopoulos, "Tuning of event-based industrial controllers with simple stability guarantees," *J. Process Control*, vol. 23, no. 9, pp. 1251–1260, Oct. 2013.

- [15] B. Hensel, J. Ploennigs, V. Vasyutynskyy, and K. Kabitzsch, "A simple PI controller tuning rule for sensor energy efficiency with level-crossing sampling," in *Proceedings of the 9th Multi-Conference on Systems, Signals and Devices*, 2012.
- [16] J. Lunze and D. Lehmann, "A state-feedback approach to event-based control," *Automatica*, vol. 46, no. 1, pp. 211–215, Jan. 2010.
- [17] U. Tiberi and K. H. Johansson, "On event-based PI control of first-order processes," in *IFAC Conference on Advances in PID Control PID'12*, 2012.
- [18] Á. Ruiz, J. E. Jiménez, J. Sánchez, and S. Dormido, "Control Basado en Eventos de Sistemas de Primer Orden Con Retardo," *Rev. Iberoam. Automática e Informática Ind.*, vol. 10, pp. 302–312, 2013.
- [19] Á. Ruiz, J. E. Jiménez, J. Sánchez, and S. Dormido, "A practical tuning methodology for event-based PI control," *J. Process Control*, vol. 24, no. 1, pp. 278–295, Jan. 2014.
- [20] J. Chacón, J. Sánchez, A. Visioli, L. Yebra, and S. Dormido, "Characterization of limit cycles for self-regulating and integral processes with PI control and send-on-delta sampling," *J. Process Control*, vol. 23, no. 6, pp. 826–838, Jul. 2013.
- [21] K. J. Åström and T. Hägglund, *Advanced PID Control*. ISA Press, Research Triangle Park, NC, 2005.
- [22] K. J. Åström, "Event based control," in *Analysis and Design of Nonlinear Control Systems: In Honor of Alberto Isidori*, Springer Verlag, 2008.
- [23] M. Beschi, S. Dormido, J. Sanchez, and A. Visioli, "Tuning rules for event-based SSOD-PI controllers," in *Proceedings of the 20th Mediterranean Conference on Control & Automation (MED)*, 2012, pp. 1073–1078.
- [24] K. J. Åström, C. Hang, and B. Lim, "A new Smith predictor for controlling a process with an integrator and long dead-time," *IEEE Trans. Automat. Contr.*, vol. 39, no. 2, pp. 343–345, 1994.
- [25] S. Skogestad, "Simple analytic rules for model reduction and PID controller tuning," *J. Process Control*, vol. 13, no. 4, pp. 291–309, Jun. 2003.